

Muridiyya of Senegal

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Entry tags: Sufi, Religious Group

The country named Senegal is a creation of French colonialism in the late nineteenth century. The majority of the population are Muslims. One of the most influential Muslim groups is the Muridiyya founded by Ahmadu Bamba at the dawn of French colonialism. The capital of Muridiyya is Touba. The Murids practice a mystic Islam. The Murids are now spread throughout the world with the largest diaspora in New York. They hold social, political, and economic power in Senegal. Ahmadu Bamba was born in a learned Muslim family and was educated by his parents. He chose Sufi path for its Islamic mysticism. He was attracted to Sufism for its asceticism and rejection of materialism in a context of the Wolof ruling class exploitation and the beginning of French colonization. He preached a peaceful Islam in his resistance against French colonialism. He privileged education because in his Sufi's conception of Islam, the war is against one's soul (nafs in Arabic) or the bestial self of human being. He conceived the Tarbiyya as a mystical pedagogy to promote good work ethic and control the nafs. He organized his disciples into working groups known as daara tarbiyya which later became villages and towns. Bamba combined a mysticism rooted in Sharia with a focus on educating the heart. Islamic jurisprudence and the oneness of God was primordial to him, and he saw them as the soul and body of Islam. He rejected extreme asceticism and sees a Murid or a disciple as being an integral part of one's community and being a mystic at the same time. The only time asceticism is allowed in Muridiyya is when the shaykh has to prepare himself for an imminent danger or when living in a politically corrupt environment where he is not listened to. His conception of Muslim education is focused on the Murid's contribution to his community. Seeking a lifelong knowledge both esoteric and exoteric should be the primary goal of the disciple and the Qur'an should be at the center of this knowledge while striving to apply this knowledge in everyday life. The Taalim or exoteric education's goal is to feed the brain, the tarbiyya or the esoteric knowledge is about strengthening the soul and the tarqiyya which is the highest and leadership level concerns a complete detachment from material world. In Bamba's teachings, the Murid student should strive early in his life to combat ignorance, to be useful to his community, to enrich the science of Islamic religion and to put in practice the teachings while submitting to his Shaykh or teacher when seeking God.

Date Range: 1853 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Senegal, West Africa

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa

The Muridiyya in Senegal

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Babou, Cheikh Anta. *Fighting the Greater Jihad: Amadu Bamba and the Founding of the Muridiyya of Senegal, 1853-1913*. Athens: Ohio University Press. 2007
- Source 2: Babou, Cheikh Anta. *The Muridiyya on the Move: Islam, Migration, and Place Making*. Athens: Ohio University Press. 2021
- Source 3: Glover, John. *Sufism and Jihad in Modern Senegal: The Murid Order*. Rochester: University of Rochester Press. 2007

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://toubamica.org/history-of-the-foundation/>
- Source 1 Description: This website depicts the history of Muridiyya and its founder.
- Source 2 URL: <https://berkleycenter.georgetown.edu/posts/church-and-state-the-clout-of-senegal-s-mouride-brotherhood>
- Source 2 Description: The information in this article describe the relation between the state and the Muridiyya

- Source 3 URL: <https://www.georgetownjournalofinternationalaffairs.org/online-edition/the-place-of-mouridism-in-senegalese-civil-society-by-alex-villeg>
- Source 3 Description: This article explains the social, economic and political power of the Murids in contemporary Senegal.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://blogs.bl.uk/a/6a00d8341c464853ef01bb08aee3d0970d-pi>
- Source 1 Description: Wolof Ajami text, credit British Library at <https://blogs.bl.uk/endangeredarchives/2016/01/deciphering-wolof-ajami-texts.html>
- Source 2 URL: <https://eap.bl.uk/project/EAP334>
- Source 2 Description: Digital preservation of Wolof Ajami manuscripts of Senegal (EAP334)
- Source 3 URL: <https://libguides.northwestern.edu/c.php?g=492192&p=3369543>
- Source 3 Description: Arabic Manuscripts from West Africa: A Catalog of the Herskovits Library Collection: Historical Context

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The members of the Muridiyya are in contact with members of other religious groups such as Christians, African traditional worshippers, and other Sufi group members such as the Tijaniyya, the Qadiriyya, and recently the Salafi who came back from Saudi Arabia with fresh ideas about what Islam should be. In general, all these groups peacefully coexist. <https://www.bouelmogdad.com/ethnic-groups-and-religions/>

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: Because a large majority of the population in Senegal is Muslim the cultural contact with other religions is less competitive.

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is more or less accommodating and pluralistic because the Islam practiced in Senegal is tolerant.

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: whether they are Muslims or Christians or from other religions, they all peacefully coexist.

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: In the 1990 there was a conflict in the Casamance region where a separatist movement was led by a Catholic priest. Recently, there was a flare in violence with the government intervening. <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-senegal-casamance/casamance-conflict-is-unhealed-sore-for-senegal-idUSTRE81O09C20120225>

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Senegal is located West African region. In the neighboring Mali, there is a violent jihadist conflict that is affecting the whole region with sporadic violence across borders.
<https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/africaatlse/2022/02/15/violent-extremism-in-the-sahel-strengthening-grip-west-africa-mali-burkina-faso-niger-jihadi/>

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: There are no assignment at birth but Muridiyya leadership remains in Ahmadu Bamba's family with the successive General Caliph being his biological descendants. For the rest of the members of the Muridiyya, children are born in families that have been Murids for generation. It is more of children practicing the religion of their parents than an assignment at birth as is the case in many Muslim families in Africa.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: The new adherent goes through an initiation known as Ahd under the supervision of his Shaykh.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Both male and female are recognized to be leaders in Muridiyya. Example of female Shaykhs are Shaykha Muslimatou Mbacke and Shaikha Maimouna Kabir.
<https://www.sacredfootsteps.org/2019/09/20/the-female-scholars-and-saints-of-senegal/>

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: In the rural areas, new disciples are initiated in the daraa (rural Islamic schooling system) while in urban areas, they are initiated in the dahiras which are prayer circles where work ethics and spirituality are inculcated in the disciple. In addition to the dahiras, the kurels or the communal singing of the qasida (performances) are practiced. The chain of authority is known as the ndigal (recommendation). It starts with the direct descendants of the founder, then between the disciple and his Shaykh. The pact of allegiance or the jebbalu establishes the blind trust and the obedience of the disciple.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The Daraa and Dahira are the platform used to proselytized. Media technologies are intensely used to attract new members.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Whether they are in the rural or urban area, attracting new disciple is a duty for religious professionals.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: The relation disciple/Shaykh is the most emphasized.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Due to Muridiyya influence in politics, there is a reciprocal support between the politicians and the Muridiyya leadership.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: The disciples through their works provide the financial support for their Shaykh.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: Most of the Murid's projects are realized by the members financial support. The best example is the construction of the mosque of Touba, the holy city of the Muridiyya constructed with the members funds. <https://www.aa.com.tr/fr/culture-et-arts/s%C3%A9n%C3%A9gal-mosqu%C3%A9e-de-touba-l-histoire-d-un-pilier-du-mouridisme/152364>

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: The Muridiyya order is led by the biological descendants of Ahmadu Bamba but the Senegalese polity is founded on a democratic political system which elects a president every five years. The head of the polity is different from the head of the religion except the city of Touba which has a special status with its own police, administration, and ruled by the Sharia.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: The majority of Senegalese are Muslims and the president except one were all Muslims. Most Muslims' holidays are observed in Senegal.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Notes: Senegal is considered as a secular state with secular laws but the city of Touba, the capital of Muridiyya is governed by the Sharia. <https://www.cmi.no/news/1625-reality-defeats-good-intentions>

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: Touba the capital of Muridiyya is exempt from taxes and duties. <https://www.ft.com/content/b6a570cc-5650-11dc-ab9c-0000779fd2ac>

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Any member who leaves the group is considered as an apostate. Due to secular nature of Senegal, the consequence of apostasy is limited to family rejection and isolation.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: Even though the city of Touba is governed by the Sharia law, the country of Senegal is a secular state where the religious freedom is guaranteed. <https://www.state.gov/reports/2020-report-on-international-religious-freedom/senegal/>

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 5000000

Notes: The population estimate is found in Cheikh Anta Babou, *The Muridiyya on the Move: Islam, Migration, and Place Making*: https://books.google.co.in/books?id=7rllEAAAQBAJ&pg=RA1-PA22&lpg=RA1-PA22&dq=the+estimate+of+Muridiyya+population+in+Senegal&source=bl&ots=k6WrBD-1Ax&sig=ACfU3U3TslV_fAswQyOUVz3RI_QdHn6nHw&hl=en&sa=X&ved=2ahUKewiww-fZn6P3AhUUV80KHTb0Bu8Q6AF6BAggEAM#v=onepage&q=the%20estimate%20of%20Muridiyya%20population%20in%20

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 31.7

Notes: The population estimate is found in Cheikh Anta Babou, *The Muridiyya on the Move: Islam, Migration, and Place Making*: https://books.google.co.in/books?id=7rllEAAAQBAJ&pg=RA1-PA22&lpg=RA1-PA22&dq=the+estimate+of+Muridiyya+population+in+Senegal&source=bl&ots=k6WrBD-1Ax&sig=ACfU3U3TslV_fAswQyOUVz3RI_QdHn6nHw&hl=en&sa=X&ved=2ahUKewiww-fZn6P3AhUUV80KHTb0Bu8Q6AF6BAggEAM#v=onepage&q=the%20estimate%20of%20Muridiyya%20population%20in%20

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Muridiyya is led by a Caliph. All the successive Caliphs are biological descendants of Ahmadu Bamba.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: The chain of authority is known as Ndigal and links hierarchically all the Shaykhs and

their disciples.

- ↳ A single leader of a local community:
 - Yes
- ↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:
 - No
- ↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):
 - Yes
- ↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:
 - Number of levels [numeric value]: 6
 - Notes: The hierarchy starts with God, followed by the prophet Muhammad, then direct descendants and early companions, followed by the Caliph General, direct descendants and the disciples.
- ↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:
 - No
 - ↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:
 - No
 - ↳ Powers are inherited:
 - Yes
 - Notes: All the religious leaders of the Muridiyya are the biological descendants of Ahmadou Bamba.
 - ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:
 - No
 - ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Powers are transmitted from teacher to disciple.
 - ↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: Because the leadership is hereditary, power is associated with leadership office.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: In Muridiyya, the leader or the Shaykh's pronouncement are indisputable and unquestionable. The disciple must obey without any questioning.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Qur'an is the sacred text of the Muridiyya. The members of the group subscribe to the idea that the Qur'an was divinely revealed the Islam prophet Muhammad.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Qur'an is a written text and revealed to the Islam prophet Muhammad in the Arabic language.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The Qur'an was divinely revealed to the Prophet of Islam Muhammad in the seventh century and is the holy book of the Muridiyya. It is reported that Muhammad was an illiterate when the Qur'an was revealed to him by Allah, the high god of Islam.
<https://www.nouracademy.com/article/Quran-Revelation>

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: It is reported that the angel Jibril or Gabriel was the one who directly revealed the Qur'an to Muhammad. Members of the Muridiyya believe in this angelic revelation.
<https://www.nouracademy.com/article/Quran-Revelation>

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Muhammad, the prophet of Islam was the one who received the Qur'an from divine revelation.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The leaders or Shaykhs are responsible for interpreting the Qur'an.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– No

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Shaykhs are the trained people allowed to transmit the scriptures.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Sharia is the codified canon of Islamic scriptures used by the Muridiyya.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The mosque of Touba is a monumental architecture built from 1887 and completed in 1963.
<https://www.bbc.com/news/av/world-africa-14395773>

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:
– Yes

↳ Temples:
– Yes

↳ Altars:
– No

↳ Devotional markers:
– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:
– Yes
Notes: Magal is the annual religious festival and one of the most important event for the Murids.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:
– On persons
– At home
– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:
– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– No

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Notes: The city of Touba and the area surrounding it, known as the eastern Bawol, were intentionally created by the founder of Muridiyya as a sacred area known in Arabic as the daara al Murid or the land of the Murid. The region as a whole is a sacred site with the intention of transforming the environment to fit the vision of the founder of the religious group. The natural environment was completely transformed into a religious site for the Muridiyya.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Each year, the members of the religious group go back to Touba for the 'great Maggal', that is the Muridiyya pilgrimage to celebrate historical events and figures of the Sufi group.
<https://foncab.org/muridism/the-magal/>

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for all

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: In his teachings, Ahmadu Bamba clearly distinguishes the spirit from the body and from the soul. He believes in training both to accomplish perfection on earth and in the other worldly realm.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:
– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:
– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The concept of afterlife in Muridiyya is rooted in what Ahmadou Bamba calls belief in the last thing. It is an eschatological belief that shape inner worldly attitudes.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:
– Yes
Notes: Paradise is described as above space.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:
– Yes
Notes: Hell is described as below space.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
– Yes [specify]: Afterlife is beyond the earth.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: Adherents practice Muslim burial with the corpse buried within 24 hours.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

Notes: Even though the group members believe in all the supernatural beings mentioned in Islam, their focus is on innerworldly ascetism and this is related to good work ethic, obedience and submission to the Shaykh, and the importance of education in social change. The focus of Muridiyya is squarely on work and religious practice and not on supernatural beings.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: They believe in the coming of the Mahdi, the eschatological messiah coming at the end of time to repair injustice in the world.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: The Mahdi whereabouts is unknown but his coming is at the end of times.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: He will rid the world with evil and injustice.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: The Mahdi will rule the whole world when he comes at the end of times.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: The Mahdi will be the last Imam that is a worship leader.

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: The exact time is unknown. It can be a near future or a distant future.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Notes: The exact time is unknown. It can be a near or a distant future.

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: The divine judgement starts when a dead person is buried. Whether the person has a favorable judgement in the grave or not, the sojourn in the grave will be good or difficult until the resurrection day for the final judgement.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: The Mahdi will lead a new politico-Islamic system.

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Those whose good deeds outweigh the bad ones will go to paradise and those whose bad deeds outweigh the good ones will go to hell.

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Murids are required to train their soul against corrupting influence. Muridiyya emphasizes good work ethics and religious practices known as Tarbiyya to keep the nafs or the lower self (or the animal instinct) to keep oneself away from worldly pleasure.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Religious moral norms are the only required norms.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - No
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Sexual activities outside marriage are forbidden.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Sexual activities outside marriage are forbidden.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is required during the month of Ramadan.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Pig meat is forbidden to the members of the Muridiyya.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Murids are Muslims and pray five times a day.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

–Hours: 1

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 1000000

Notes: The Maggal or the pilgrimage to the city of Touba gathers Murids once a year to celebrate together their saints and perform rituals.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 72

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Murids perform male circumcision.

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Female members have to cover their heads.

↳ Dress:
– Yes

↳ Ornaments:
– Yes

Notes: Women are allowed to wear jewelry.

↳ Archaic ritual language:
– No

↳ Other:
– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:
– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:
– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:
– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:
– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The formal education is provided by the state.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Group's adherents interact with state bureaucracy.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: Shaykh Abdoul Ahad Mbacké, caliph of the Muridiyya from 1968 to 1988, contributed through his leadership to the development of Touba's infrastructure: extension of the mosque (from 4,000 to 6,000 seats), electrification of the city, parceling of the land, installation of the telephone network, construction of ten boreholes, an airport, and a bus station. All these achievements were done with a minimal participation of the state and with the overwhelming contributions of the group members. https://www.senegal-online.com/tourisme_au_senegal/villes-et-villages-du-senegal/touba/

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:
– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The state laws are the formal legal code of the group.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Arabic and Wolof are the two languages used.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The French language is the official language of Senegal and used by members of the group.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Islamic calendar is used for religious matters (sacred) and the Gregorian calendar is used in everyday life (profane).

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Gregorian calendar is used by all Senegalese including Murids.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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